

**DEPRESSION AMONG ADOLESCENTS IN RELATION TO FAMILY
ENVIRONMENT, GENDER AND TYPE OF INSTITUTION:
A CASE STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Depression is a major health problem in India, contributing to significant morbidity, disability as well as mortality, along with significant socioeconomic issues.. About 8% of children and adolescents suffer from depression and 11% of adolescents have a depressive disorder by the age of 18 years according to the National Co-morbidity Survey-Adolescent Supplement. This study has been conducted to estimate the prevalence of depression among adolescents studying in Government and Private schools in Rajouri district of Jammu and Kashmir in order to find out a relationship between family environment, gender and types of institution. The research study was descriptive in nature. 200 adolescent was randomly selected for the study. Beck's Depression inventory and Family environment scale was administered for the study. The findings of the study revealed that majority of the adolescents have severe level of depression and there is a significant relationship between depression and family environment.

Keywords: Depression, Adolescents, Family Environment, Gender, Type of Institution

A) INTRODUCTION AND RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Depression is a mental disorder that presents with depressed mood, loss of interest or pleasure, feelings of guilt or low self-worth, disturbed sleep or appetite, low energy and poor concentration. Depression in childhood and adolescence may be similar to adult major depressive disorder, although younger

sufferers may exhibit increased irritability or aggressive and self-destructive behaviours, rather than the all-encompassing sadness associated with adult forms of depression (Birmaher et al., 1996). Petersen et. al. (1993) defined adolescent depression at three levels: (1) depressed mood, (2) depressive syndrome and (3) clinical depression. Depressed mood is sadness at various times in response to an unhappy situation. Depressive syndrome is experiencing anxiety with other symptoms such as feeling sad, lonely, unloved and worthless. Clinical depression is manifestation of five or more depressive symptoms lasting continuously for two weeks and impairing current functioning. The prevalence of depression is increasing in successive generations with onset at earlier ages.

Depression in adolescents is a disabling condition that is associated with serious long term morbidities and even suicide. It is a psychological disorder that affects a person mood changes, physical functions and social interactions. About 8% of children and adolescents suffer from depression (Valsamma and Rudi, 2012). Although Cash (2004) stated that adolescent and adult females were diagnosed with a depressive disorder twice as often as males, boys up to age 12 are as likely to suffer from depression as girls. About 11% adolescents have a depressive disorder by the age of 18 years according to the National Co-morbidity Survey-Adolescent Supplement (NCS-A). The research done by Kovacs et al. (1984) had suggested that the prevalence of young depression sufferers in Western cultures ranges from 1.9-3.4% among primary school children and 3.2-8.9% among adolescents. It has also found that among children diagnosed with a depressive episode, there is a 70% rate of recurrence within five years. Like their adult counterparts, children and adolescent depression sufferers are at an increased risk of attempting or committing suicide. In the 1990s, the National Institute of Medical Health found that up to 7% of adolescents who develop major depressive disorder may commit suicide as young adults (Weissman et al., 1999). Studies in the last decades have shown the rates of depression in adolescents to range from 8% to above 20% (Steinhausen and Metze, 2000; Bahls, 2000; Gorenstein et al., 2005) and associated with suicide, other psychiatric co-morbidity, academic

failure, poor peer relationships, substance abuse and severe depression during adulthood (Lewinsohn et al., 1993). Till date, there are only few reported studies over depression among adolescents in India. A study done by Nair et al. (2004) that specifically assessed depression reported a prevalence of 3% in 13-19 year old school going adolescents. Psychiatric morbidity among school samples of adolescents was found in about 29% of girls and 23% of boys with depression being the most common disorder (Sidana and Nijhawan, 1999). However, depression during adolescence is associated often with suicide; a phenomenon that is also on the rise among adolescents in India in recent times (Sanjeev et al., 2004). On this backdrop, this study has been conducted to estimate the prevalence of depression among adolescents studying in Government and Private school of Rajouri District of Jammu and Kashmir in order to study the levels of depression among adolescents and to find out the relationship of depression with the family environment and also to study the significant differences between gender, types of institution and family environment on measures of depression.

B) OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study depression level of adolescents.
2. To study relationship between depression and family environment.
3. To study significant difference between males and females adolescent on measures of depression.
4. To study significant differences between Government and Private school adolescents on measures of depression.
5. To study significant differences between high family environment and low family environment of adolescents on measures of depression.

C) HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There will be no significant difference between males and females adolescent on measures of depression.
2. There will be no significant differences between Government and Private school adolescents on measures of depression.
3. There will be no significant differences between high family environment and

low family environment of adolescents on measures of depression.

D) METHODOLOGY AND PROCEDURE

I. Selection of the sample

The Present study has been conducted on one of the district of Jammu and Kashmir i.e., Rajouri, from which 10 Government and Private School students of class XI was randomly taken as a sample. A sample of 200 students which include 100 boys and 100 Girls were drawn randomly from 5 Private Higher Secondary schools and 5 Government Higher secondary schools of Rajouri district.

II. Design of the study

The subjects was divided onto two sub groups of Gender i.e. Boys (n= 100) and Girls (n=100), these subjects were further divided into two sub groups based on Type of Schools based on Govt. School Adolescents (n=100) and Private School Adolescents (n=100). Further the adolescents was categorized into high family environment and low family environment based on their scores of family environment using Quartile.

III. Variables Studied

a) Dependent Variable

➤ Depression

b) Independent variables

➤ Types of School (High/Low)

➤ Gender (Boys and Girls)

➤ Family Environment (High/ Low)

IV. Selection of the tools

The Beck depression Inventory and Family Environment Scale by Dr. Harpreet Bhatia and N.K Chadha was administered on randomly selected students.

V. Procedure

The instruments/tools were administered to all the 200 subjects individually in face to face situations. Instructions given in the respective manuals were

followed while administering and scoring of the test.

E) RESULTS

Table 1: Showing the level of depression of adolescents.

Levels of depression	Frequency	Mean	%
Normal	11	11/200	5.5%
Mild	26	26/200	13%
Moderate	72	72/200	36%
Severe	91	91/200	45.5%

The above table shows that minor i.e., 5.5% adolescents have normal depression, 13% belongs to mild, 36% belongs to moderate and 45.5% have severe levels of depression.

Table 2: Showing the level of depression of adolescents (Boys).

Levels of depression	Frequency	Mean	%
Normal	06	06/100	6%
Mild	12	12/100	12%
Moderate	29	29/100	29%
Severe	53	53/100	53%

The above table shows that minor i.e., 6% boys have normal depression, 12% belongs to mild, 29% belongs to moderate and 53% have severe depression level.

Table 3: Showing the level of depression of adolescents (Girls).

Level of depression	Frequency	Mean	%
Normal	05	05/100	5%
Mild	14	14/100	14%
Moderate	43	43/40	43%
Severe	38	38/40	38%

The above table shows that minor i.e., 5% girls falls in normal depression, 14% belongs to mild, 43% belongs to moderate and 38% belongs to severe and 43% of

the adolescents' girls belongs to moderate level of depression.

Table 4 : Showing the relationship between depression and family environment.

Group	Level of Depression	Sample Size(N)	Correlation Coefficient (r)
High Family environment	High	25	-0.24
Low Family environment	High	25	0.53

Values of coefficient of correlation depicted in the above table reveal that there is a high positive correlation between low family environment scores and high levels of depression which is 0.53. Value of 0.53 depicts the positive correlation between the family environment and depression scores for the sample. Whereas coefficient of correlation for the relationship between high family environment and high depression of -0.24 also supports that there is a negative relationship between family environment and depression which needs further research.

Table 5: showing the significant differences between male and female adolescents on measures of depression.

	Mean	Mean difference	t-value	Significance
Male Adolescents	31.94	6.3	4.224	Significant
Female Adolescents	26.88			

The t-value for the difference in the depression of male adolescents and female adolescents is 4.224 which is higher than the table value of 2.58 and is significant at 0.01 level. So, the hypothesis for no difference between male and female adolescents on the measure of depressions is rejected. Moreover the mean difference for the

depression level among male and female also supports the rejection of the hypothesis as male adolescents have high level of depression than their female counterparts which needs to be further explored.

Table 6 Showing the significant differences between high family environment and low family environment of adolescent on measures of depression.

	Mean	Mean difference	t-value	Significance
High Family Environment	27.28			
Low Family Environment	33.58	6.3	5.356	Significant

The t-value for the difference in the depression of adolescent belonging to high family environment and low family environment is 5.356 which is higher than the table value of 2.58 and is significant at 0.01 level. So, the hypothesis for no difference between the high family environment and low family environment on the measure of depression is rejected. Moreover the mean difference for the depression level among the adolescents belonging to high family environment and low family environment also supports the rejection of the hypothesis as adolescents with low family environment have high level of depression than high family environment which needs to be further explored.

Table 7 Showing the significant differences between Government and Private school adolescent on measures of depression.

	Mean	Mean difference	t-value	Significance
Govt. School Adolescents	29.42			
Pvt. School Adolescents	27.27	6.3	0.064	Not Significant

The t- value for the difference in the depression among Government schools adolescent and Private school adolescents is 0.064 which is lower than the table

value of 1.96 and is not significant. So, the hypothesis for no difference between adolescents of different schools is accepted on the measure of depression.

F) CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Majority i.e., 45.5% of the adolescent have severe level of depression.
- 2) Majority i.e., 53% of the adolescent boys have severe level of depression.
- 3) Majority i.e., 43% of the adolescent girls have moderate level of depression.
- 4) 29% of the adolescent boys have moderate level of depression.
- 5) 38% of the adolescent girls have severe level of depression.
- 6) Significant relationship found between the depression and family environment of the adolescents.
- 7) Significant difference found between male and female adolescents on the measures of depression.
- 8) Significant difference found between high family environment and low family environment of adolescents on the measures of depression.
- 9) No Significant difference found between Government and Private School adolescents on the measures of depression.

G) IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study has shown a high level of depression among the school going adolescents of Rajouri district of Jammu and Kashmir. Considering that 81.5% of adolescents in this study reported moderate to severe depression, it is understood that a considerable number of adolescents are experiencing turmoil during this phase. This could result in further problems like poor academic performance, poor coping methods and suicidal ideations. Further the study also revealed the relationship between family environment and depression. This finding emphasizes the need for screening for depressive symptomatology and identifying adolescents who need further intervention. Similar studies like the current one could pave the way for school-based interventions that may help adolescents with mild and moderate depressive symptoms which in turn could minimize the risk for progression into other serious problems like drug abuse, suicide and violence. Based on the findings in this study there is need to carry out a more comprehensive study in schools to

determine the various psychosocial factors for depression in adolescents with the purpose of developing intervention policies.

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